

ENERGY CONSERVATION IN TRACTION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Automatic tunnel Light Control System is a simple yet powerful concept, which uses transistor as a switch. By using this system manual work are 100% removed. It automatically switches ON and OFF lights. When train enters towards the tunnel lights are ON by using PIC microcontroller and sensors. When train is completely gone out of tunnel lights are OFF. By using this system energy consumption is also reduced because now a days the manually operated tunnel lights are not switched off even. In this project, no Need of manual operation likes ON time and OFF time setting by makes use of the transistor switching condition PIC controller operates the light through relay. Supply uses 230/9 V transformer is used.

KEYWORDS: PIC microcontroller, relay, 230/9 V transformer